

HOSPITAL DIVERSITY

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Introduction

Healthcare cultural competence is the ability to offer care to patients from diverse backgrounds and with a different set of beliefs and behaviors by customizing healthcare delivery to meet diverse patients' needs. Such barriers as language barriers and literacy gap and cultural differences have hindered effective communication between nurses and patients from diverse communities calling for the need to use care delivery models such as patient-centered medical homes and accountable care organizations.

Overview

One of the largest Chicago teaching and research hospitals with 645-bed capacity put a special focus on improving the cultural awareness of its staff to enhance its connection with the local ethnic communities to become culturally competent. This was also a move to help counter one of the biggest challenges that the nursing staff faced due to knowledge lack on different cultures, language barriers and socioeconomic and ethnic barriers.

A diversity group made up of nursing staff was formed to organize cultural awareness events to provide nurses with the opportunity to interact with people from different cultures representing the communities served by the hospital. This was done in order to overcome barriers that would affect patient care outcomes. The hospital surveyed the local communities to

identify opportunities and potential obstacles for providing care to the diverse community to engage the local communities.

The hospital also developed resources necessary to becoming culturally competent to embrace the range of cultures in the community that celebrates over 30 different ethnic holidays and speaks 73 languages. It created cultural competence department made up of cultural initiatives coordinator as the head, cultural competence vice president, multilingual and multicultural individuals. This department saw to the translation of hospital signage and care delivery forms into five primary languages spoken in the community.

The cultural competence of the hospital is still being expanded despite the progress seen in providing culturally competent care to the ethnically diverse patient population and improving patient outcomes due to culturally empowered nursing staff. Due to enhanced cultural awareness and competence among the nursing staff, patients in need of special care modeled are effectively attended to identify ethnic beliefs or practices quickly.

The effectiveness of the cultural competence initiatives in the hospital is tracked by looking at the local community patient bed occupancy and number (Truong, Paradies & Priest, 2014). This resulted in increased patients from the diverse local community and the growth of area ethnic and religious groups thereby increasing the hospital's consistent occupancy. The hospital also witnessed improved patient outcomes and high patient satisfaction scores in relation to healthcare delivery.

Nursing cultural competence benefits

Cultural competence has numerous benefits to care provision organizations, patients and community apart from improved patient outcomes increased respect, increased local community participation, reduced care provision costs and improved understanding. Social benefits include:

- ✓ Increased trust,
- ✓ Community participation and health issues involvement,
- ✓ Assisting families and patients in their care,
- ✓ Promoting inclusion, increased respect and understanding with patients
- ✓ and promoted health responsibilities.

Health benefits include:

- ✓ Improved collection of data,
- ✓ Reduced missed medical visits,
- ✓ Reduced care costs due to reduced medical errors,
- ✓ Increased preventive care
- ✓ and reduced patient population care disparities.

Business benefits include:

- ✓ Increased organizational market share,
- ✓ Improved care service delivery,
- ✓ Increased conformation and adherence to legal and regulatory guidelines,
- ✓ Reduced progress barriers
- ✓ and incorporation of different perspectives, strategies, and ideas in the decision-making process.

Care provision organizations and systems are faced with cultural diversity problems brought about by the increased population of immigrants due to opening opportunities in employment and education (Mareno & Hart, 2014). Hospitals are working to reduce disparities in healthcare provision and are promoting diversity in governance and leadership within the organizations. They are also educating their clinical and nursing staff on how to approach unique cultural and linguistic factors that affect care for patients from diverse communities. Most care organizations are increasingly training nurses on diversity to fill in the emerging gap in patient care in order to improve patient outcomes.

Conclusion

Healthcare organizations and systems must prepare their nurses and clinicians how to interact with diverse patient backgrounds as these increase patient engagement and education and eliminate ethnic and racial disparities in care provision. People with diverse values, behaviors, and beliefs need improved cultural competence among the nursing staff for appropriate care provision. Hospitals and other care provision facilities and systems are increasingly incorporating cultural diversity in their vision and mission statements to reduce care variations attributed to cultural disparities and train their nurses to cultural competence.

Care provision organizations must, therefore, understand the importance of cultural diversity competent nurses in providing care to diverse patients and communities. The organizations must first understand patient population and community background, significance and effect of cultural influences on the delivery of care and the skills nurses need (Hart & Mareno, 2014). The nursing community should be trained using effective educational programs including cultural assessment, multiple methods of training, continuous teaching programs and

measurement and tracking the effects of the initiatives. Cultural competence among the nursing staff improves patient outcomes, increase mutual understand and respect with patients and also increases the local community participation.

References

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